

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF METONYMIC MODELS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LINGUISTIC CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract. The article presents a comparative analysis of metonymy as a cognitive mechanism in Russian and Uzbek languages. Universal and nationally specific models of metonymic transfers are identified, and the cognitive functions of metonymy in conceptualizing reality are determined. Based on lexicographic sources and literary texts, the national-cultural specificity of metonymic transfers is established, conditioned by differences in the conceptualization of reality characteristic of Russian and Uzbek linguistic cultures. The research results confirm the position that metonymy is an important means of conceptualizing reality, reflecting both universal cognitive mechanisms and the national-cultural specificity of linguistic consciousness.

Keywords: metonymy, cognitive mechanism, Russian language, Uzbek language, comparative analysis, conceptualization, national-cultural specificity, linguistic culture, metonymic transfer models.

Introduction. Metonymy as a universal cognitive mechanism plays a significant role in forming the linguistic worldview and provides conceptualization and categorization of reality. Despite the significant number of studies devoted to metonymy in individual languages, a comparative analysis of metonymy functioning in typologically different languages, such as Russian and Uzbek, remains a poorly studied area.

Methodology. The study is based on an integrative approach combining methods of cognitive linguistics, comparative linguistics, and linguoculturology. The main methods are:

Comparative-typological method for identifying common and specific features of metonymy in Russian and Uzbek languages.

Cognitive modeling for reconstructing metonymic models.

Component analysis for identifying semantic components in the structure of metonymic meanings.

Contextual analysis for studying metonymy functioning in text.

Linguoculturological analysis for identifying the national-cultural specificity of metonymic transfers.

The research material included lexicographic sources (explanatory dictionaries of Russian and Uzbek languages), literary works in Russian and Uzbek (20th-21st centuries), journalistic texts in Russian and Uzbek, and data from national corpora of Russian and Uzbek languages.

Results. Analysis of theoretical concepts of metonymy in foreign, Russian, and Uzbek linguistics showed the evolution of views from understanding metonymy as a simple name transfer and rhetorical device (antique tradition) to recognizing its role as a cognitive mechanism and means of conceptualizing reality (cognitive tradition).

In the Russian linguistic tradition, the emphasis is placed on the regularity of metonymic models and their role in semantic derivation (N.D. Arutyunova, E.V. Paducheva, D.N. Shmelev), while in the Uzbek tradition, the focus is on the national-cultural specificity of metonymic associations (E.R. Kilichev, A.M. Mamatov, D.U. Ashurova).

Metonymy as a cognitive mechanism is characterized by the following features:

1. **Conceptuality:** Metonymy is not limited to language but represents a way of thinking, perception, and experience organization.
2. **Referentiality:** Metonymy provides access to one conceptual entity through another.
3. **Conceptuality:** Metonymic relationships are established within a single conceptual domain or cognitive model.
4. **Motivation:** Metonymic connections are based on objective contiguity relations between objects of the real world.
5. **Pragmatism:** Metonymy serves pragmatic purposes of cognitive effort economy and emphasizing certain aspects of a situation.

Discussion. The research results allow us to conclude that metonymy as a cognitive mechanism has both universal and nationally specific features in Russian and Uzbek languages.

The universality of metonymy is manifested in the presence of common models of metonymic transfers based on objective contiguity relations between objects of the real world. This confirms the cognitive linguistics position that metonymy is a fundamental cognitive mechanism with a biological basis in the characteristics of human perception and thinking.

The national-cultural specificity of metonymy is due to differences in the conceptualization of reality characteristic of Russian and Uzbek linguistic cultures. In the Russian language, metonymy often reflects state-political

realities and geographical features, which is associated with the historical development of Russian culture. In the Uzbek language, metonymy is more closely connected with traditional values, craft traditions, and kinship relations, which is due to the specifics of Uzbek culture.

Conclusion. The conducted research allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Metonymy is a universal cognitive mechanism that has both common and specific features in different languages.

2. The national-cultural specificity of metonymy is manifested in reflecting various aspects of reality characteristic of Russian and Uzbek linguistic cultures.

The research results can be used in teaching lexicology, cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, and in translation practice. Prospects for further research are associated with studying the dynamics of metonymic models in diachrony, as well as with a comparative analysis of metonymy in other typologically different languages.

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